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History of Contaminated Air – From 1901 to 2021

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Abstract

Purpose: This document identifies the historical aspects of aircraft contaminated air.

Findings: The problem was first known in early 1950s. There are over 150 pieces of research and other initiatives to date. It is an acknowledged flight safety issue. FAA and EASA are failing to mitigate to flight safety problem or protect crew and public health. We find increasing legal actions against airlines and aircraft manufacturers. Effective total cabin air filtration and onboard sensors are needed to enhance flight safety and protect public health.

Keywords

contaminated air, fume events, oil fumes, flight safety, bleed air, aerotoxic syndrome

1 Dawn of Aviation

The first flight took place in 1903, by 1909 the English Channel was flown and in 1919, Alcock and Brown crossed the Atlantic. In 1927, Charles Lindbergh flew solo non-stop from New York to Paris in 33.5 hours. Aviation progress was staggering. Aviation was here to stay.

To make air travel more comfortable and more economical, flight at higher altitudes was needed. To enable this, aircraft would need to be pressurised. The first aircraft with a pressurised cockpit was the Engineering Division USD-9A (**Figure 1, Figure 2**), that flew in 1921 but the first pressurised commercial airliner was the Boeing Model 307 Stratoliner, which first flew in 1938.

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Figure 1 Engineering Division USD-9A.

Figure 2 USD-9A with pressurised cockpit (SDASM 2010).

2 Beginning of the Jet Age and Propeller Driven Commercial Aircraft

The following year, in 1939, aviation took another technological leap forward when the Heinkel He 178 (Figure 3) became the world's first aircraft to fly under turbojet power, and the first practical jet aircraft. Only 8 years later Chuck Yeager broke the sound barrier in October 1947.

Figure 3 Heinkel He 178.

The Boeing Model 307 (Figure 4) used cabin superchargers to pump high volumes of air into the aircraft to provide an 8,000 foot cabin altitude whilst flying at 15,000 feet. The Cabin Blowers revolutionised aircraft and provided the air needed for pressurisation. Adverts from companies like AiResearch called them the 'New "Lungs" For The Luxury Airliners'. These very effective blowers flew on 1940s aircraft like the Lockheed L647/749 Constellation (Figure 5) and Boeing B-29 Superfortress.

Figure 4 Boeing Model 307 Stratoliner.

Figure 5 Lockheed L-647 Constellation.

However, the introduction of the jet engine offered a new way of pressurising the aircraft cabin - Air from the engine. When the Lockheed F-80 Shooting Star (**Figure 6**) flew in 1944, air was taken from the engine blower section and used to pressurise the cockpit. This provided an 18,000 foot cabin altitude whilst flying at 30,000 feet.

Figure 6 Lockheed F-80 Shooting Star (McLaren 2004).

"In the early 1950s, the J57 engine took jet engine design to new levels and air was bled off the compression section of the axial flow engine (**Figure 7**). These new engines operated at far higher internal temperatures and needed a new type of oil to replace the previously used mineral oil. These new oils developed under military specification MIL-L-7808 were man made synthetic oils known as Type One or Three centistoke oils." (Loraine 2019)

Figure 7 Extraction of bleed air from the compression section (GCAQE 2015).

As US military pilots started to fly these higher-powered aircraft with the new synthetic engine oils, the problem of contaminated air emerged. Reports of heated engine oil contaminating the unfiltered breathing air supply and impacting health and flight safety, soon started to emerge. The problem was linked to oil leaking past the engine bearing oil seals and contaminating the breathing air.

Numerous agencies and aircraft manufacturers investigated this emerging problem. The US Air Force concluded the toxicity was derived from the thermal decomposition of the oils base stock. They also predicted there would be increased toxicity as engine temperatures increased. (Treon 1955)

Single seat US military planes soon saw crews required to wear oxygen masks from take off to landing. This mitigated but did not resolve the problem.

3 Early Commercial Jet Aircraft

In the early commercial jet aircraft, to prevent oil contamination of the air supply (known as 'bleed air') turbo compressors were used on all the early US passenger jet aircraft such as the Boeing 707, Douglas DC-8, and Convair 880/990 (Figure 8). The corresponding switches and gauges could be found on the flight engineer's panel (Figure 9).

Figure 8 Convair 880.

Figure 9 Cabin compressor switches on the flight engineer's panel (Convair 880).

However, turbo compressors were the effective solution but also the heaviest, most complicated and least economical option. Despite the known concerns in the US, two European aircraft manufacturers elected to use direct bleed air on the French Caravelle (Figure 10) and later versions of the British Comet aircraft.

Figure 10 Sud Aviation Caravelle (Garrard 1967).

Soon US aircraft manufacturers followed suit and in 1962 the British Vickers VC-10 aircraft became the last commercial airline to not use bleed air.

The industry had convinced itself that the air within the engine used to supply the bleed air, was of the same quality as the outside air. If there were to be occasional fume events, the air supplied by the bleed air system was deemed to be acceptable. (NRC 2002)

4 Contemporary Commercial Jet Aircraft

Reports of contaminated air continued over the next decades. It was only when the smoking ban on passenger jet aircraft arrived in the late 1980s, early 1990s that the number of fume events escalated.

By the end of 2000, the US Senate had been informed and an Australian Senate Inquiry had concluded that contaminated air was a health and flight safety issue. By 2007 air accident investigation departments had twice recommended all aircraft have contaminated air warning systems following a number of crew and pilot impairments and incapacitations in flight due to exposures.

In 2009, the Boeing 787 became the only aircraft to fly without using bleed air for pressurisation, it has a bleed free architecture utilising electrical compressors.

As of September 2021, no commercial jet airliner flies with any effective bleed air filtration or warning systems fitted.

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